

First record of the trash-line spider *Cyclosa conica* (Pallas, 1772) from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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ABSTRACT: We present the first records of the trash-line spider *Cyclosa conica* (Pallas, 1772) from South Africa. The general morphology of live specimens is discussed with notes on their behaviour, distribution, and conservation status.

Key words: biodiversity, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Cyclosa* Menge, 1866 is a large genus known from 177 species and subspecies (World Spider Catalog, 2023). The African *Cyclosa* species have not yet been revised and only three species are presently recorded from Africa and only two are listed from South Africa.

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), a large number of specimens from several localities in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) were sampled. However, a large percentage of Araneidae specimens sampled is difficult to identify to species level. While working through the SANSA Virtual Museum photographic database, a female specimen in her trash line web was positively identified as *Cyclosa conica* (Pallas, 1772). Features of the species were compared with illustrations and the original description of the species.

Cyclosa conica is a small orb weaver that is easily recognised by the shape of the abdomen. The species is very widely spread and is known from North America, Europe, to the Far East. It is here for the first time recorded from South Africa where it was sampled from KwaZulu-Natal, but more unidentified specimens are possibly housed in natural history collections in South Africa.

TAXONOMY

In the World Spider Catalog (2023), more than 50 references are listed for *C. conica*. Total length of females 4-7 mm and males 3-5. The female can be recognised by the shape and colour of the abdomen. Abdomen bulging anteriorly, with large angular tubercle posteriorly, sometimes with additional smaller humps; caudal hump can vary in length; dorsum decorated with indistinct brownish pattern (Figs 1–3); legs pale, with indistinct dark bands at tip of most segments. Epigyne with sclerotised lobe on each side of scape; scape of epigynum tapered toward posterior end (Fig. 5). In male, carapace brownish, somewhat paler anteriorly, strongly narrowed toward front. Legs pale, with indistinct dark bands; tibia II somewhat stouter and with somewhat longer macrosetae than tibia I; coxa IV with 1 or 2 small macrosetae ventrally (Fig. 4). Male palp with median apophysis heavily sclerotised and its distal tip folded over (Fig. 6) (Levi, 1977).

LIFE STYLE

The name “*Cyclosa*” comes from the Greek “to move in a circle” and refers to how it spins its web. They make a complete vertical, closely woven orb-web in vegetation, about one metre above the ground. The distinguishing character of the web is the vertical stabilimentum that runs down the centre of the web, in line with the hub (Fig. 2).

Figures 1–2. *Cyclosa conica* female in orb-web from Pinetown
Photo credits: Johan van Zyl.

Figures 3–6. *Cyclosa conica* line drawings. 3. Female lateral view. 4. Male lateral view. 5. Epigyne. 6. Male palp. Credits: After Levi (1977).

The female in her web was found on a shrub. The orb is wider than long, with 40 to 50 radii (Fig. 7) and it lacks a retreat. The stabilimentum is composed of dead prey and other debris that are woven together with silk (Fig. 8). The spider hides in this debris as a defense against predators (Fig. 2). The spider hangs in the centre with legs folded around the body (Fig. 1). The natural coloration of members of *Cyclosa* makes it extremely difficult to see, and only when it moves, the spider is spotted (Figs 7–8) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022a).

According to Dondale (2002), mature males do not build orb-webs. The females produce three to five egg sacs that are elliptical, yellowish brown, and are attached to dead twigs or under leaves, but not to the orb-web.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

North America, Europe, Turkey, Caucasus, Russia, Iran, Central Asia, China. New: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

KwaZulu-Natal: Pinetown (-29.81, 30.85).

CONSERVATION STATUS

Due to wide global range listed as Least Concern.

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Figures 7–8. *Cyclosa conica* female photographed on 7 March, 2020 in an orb-web in Pinetown, KwaZulu-Natal. Photo credits Johan van Zyl.